

Freedom of expression in the Western Balkans through the lens of the ECHR

Rilind Berisha

PhD Candidate, South East European University, Tetova, North Macedonia

Article DOI: [10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0604](https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0604)

DOI URL: <https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0604>

KEYWORDS: Freedom of expression, Western Balkans, Comparative legal analysis, Human rights protection

ABSTRACT: Freedom of expression is a fundamental right guaranteed by Article 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and represents one of the main pillars of a democratic society. In the context of the Western Balkans, this right finds support not only in domestic legislation, but also in the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights. This research paper provides a comparative and substantive analysis of the ECHR ruling related to freedom of expression in six countries of the region: Albania, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and examines the specific case of Kosovo. The results show that most countries have been found to be in violation of the 10th Article due to disproportionate restrictions on expression. The case of Kosovo, although yet not member of the Council of Europe, represents a positive exception due to the direct incorporation of the ECHR jurisprudence into the Constitution. The study concludes that effective protection of freedom of expression requires not only formal respect for the law, but also an institutional culture that promotes and guarantees this right in practice.

Corresponding Author:

Rilind Berisha

Published: June 09, 2025

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1. INTRODUCTION

Freedom of expression is a guaranteed. Freedom of expression includes the right to express oneself, to disseminate and receive information, opinions and other messages without impediment (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo (2008), Article 40, Par. 1). The exercise of this freedom, which carries with it obligations and responsibilities, may be subject to certain restrictions or sanctions provided for by law and which, in a democratic society, constitute necessary measures such as: national security, territorial integrity and public safety, the protection of public order and peace and the prevention of crime, the protection of health and morals, the protection of the dignity or rights of others, the prohibition and dissemination of secret information, or the guarantee of the authority and impartiality of the judiciary. (Bajrami, 2012).

Freedom of expression is one of the fundamental pillars of a democratic society and an indispensable right for the personal and social development of the individual. In this context, the countries of the Western Balkans, which aim the integration into European Union and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) structures, are called upon to meet the highest standards in the protection of human rights. One of the most important mechanisms for guaranteeing this right is the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), which operated under the European Convention on Human Rights, where the 10th Article sanctions the right of freedom of expression. In the Western Balkan region, this right has faced numerous challenges due to authoritarian legacies, political polarization and interethnic conflicts. The European Court of Human Rights has played an important role in shaping standards on freedom of expression in this region, influencing states' approach to restricting speech, particularly when it comes to "hate speech", "religious insults" and "radical political discourse".

This paper examines how this right is applied and interpreted by the ECHR in relation to the Western Balkan states: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia. A special attention is paid to the Republic of Kosovo, which, although it is not yet part of the Council of Europe, has integrated in its Constitution the direct implementation of the Convention and the Judicial practice of the ECHR.

Through this paper, it is intended to evaluate the effectiveness of the ECHR in influencing the justice systems of these countries to guarantee freedom of expression, to identify the existing shortcomings in practice and to suggest concrete improvements for greater harmonization with international standards. This analysis is important to understand not only the role of the ECHR in this area, but also the capacity of the states of the region to protect and promote basic human rights.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper uses a comparative and analytical approach, examining the decisions of the ECHR relating to freedom of expression in the Western Balkan countries. The data is collected from primary sources – official decisions published in the ECHR HUDOC database – and secondary sources, such as relevant literature and constitutional legal documents of the countries involved.

The analysis is broken down by country, assessing:

- The number of cases that have reached the ECHR,
- The outcome of these cases (whether a violation was found or not),
- The nature of the claims and the conclusions of the ECHR.

For Kosovo, due to its non-membership in the Council of Europe, the methodology of reviewing the decisions of the Constitutional Court and regular courts that refer to the practice of the ECHR has been used.

The aim of this methodology is to draw balanced conclusions, based on facts and legal precedents, and to identify the approach that states follow in interpreting and implementing Article 10 of the ECHR. This methodology also helps in understanding the impact of international law on national law and promotes the implementation of European human rights standards.

3. BETWEEN THE NORM AND THE PRACTICE: FREEDOM OF SPEECH IN EUROPEAN AND BALKAN JURISPRUDENCE

One of the characteristics of the ECHR's jurisprudence is the constant tension between the protection of freedom of expression and the need to combat intolerance. In numerous cases, as Koen Lemmens points out, the ECHR often shows ambiguity in the distinction between free expression and hate speech, which has resulted in inconsistent and contradictory jurisprudence for member states, including the Western Balkans (Lemmens, 2015). Everyone has the right to freedom of expression. This right shall include freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart information and ideas without interference by public authority and regardless of frontiers. This Article shall not prevent States from requiring the licensing of broadcasting, television or cinema enterprises (European Court of Human Rights, 2021).

This is how the ECHR defines freedom of expression, which today constitutes the most important definition of this right, always with regard to countries that are part of the Council of Europe, but also to countries like the Republic of Kosovo that have the ECHR as part of their domestic law¹.

Freedom of expression is part of the group of civil and political rights, along with other rights such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial, the right to vote, etc. As such, it is also sanctioned by the constitutions of the respective states, so that the constitutional elements of this freedom are:

- Freedom of speech, public appearance and public information is guaranteed;
- The right to freely establish institutions for public information is guaranteed, as provided by law;
- Free access to information, freedom to receive and impart information is guaranteed;
- The right to accountability in the media is guaranteed;
- The right to improvement in the public information media is guaranteed;
- The right to protection of the source of information in the public information media is guaranteed
- And that Censorship is prohibited (Bajrami, 2012).
- Freedom of expression as a human right is categorized as follows:
 - Active freedom of expression – includes the right of people to express their opinions, namely to share them with others;
 - Passive freedom of expression – includes the right of people not to be forced to share or express their opinions with others;
 - The right to be informed – includes the right of people to be informed by others, mainly from the media, governmental and non-governmental institutions, etc., about general and important information for a democratic society;
 - The right to inform - includes the right of people to inform others about information that they possess, which is of interest to a democratic society. This right is presented with the obligation that the subject who distributes this information not be sanctioned, namely not to suffer consequences for having distributed certain information, which by the legislation of that state has not been decisively prohibited for distribution, or that the distribution of that data has constituted a threat to national security, etc.

The main elements of freedom of expression are:

- Freedom to hold opinions without interference (freedom of opinion);
- Freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas (freedom of expression, freedom of information):
 - Orally, in writing, in print and in form of art (Benedek and Nikolova, 2003),
 - Through all media (freedom of the media),
 - Without considering borders (freedom of international communications).

¹ For more info: Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo (2008), Article 22

In addition to interested parties, such as the media, national and international judicial institutions have also contributed to the development of the right to freedom of expression. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the role of the ECHR and the European Court of Human Rights, which has increasingly expanded Article 10 of the ECHR², by constantly advancing the right to freedom of expression, and minimizing the possibility of states to restrict it. But, in addition to the role of the European Court of Human Rights, a special role has also been played by the constitutions of the respective states, which have defined freedom of expression as a constitutional right, thus guaranteeing constitutional protection of this right, and that through efficient and effective legal instruments. The Western Balkan states, Albania, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina³, recognize the right to freedom of expression, but none of them has a consolidated tradition in the development of this right, but each of them has faced and continues to face the challenge of developing, protecting and consolidating freedom of expression as a fundamental human right.

The protection of freedom of expression in the Western Balkan countries is not only carried out by domestic justice institutions, including regular courts and national Constitutional Courts of the respective countries, but in addition to them, the European Court of Human Rights has a very special role in protecting and guaranteeing freedom of expression. Consequently, in addition to the domestic law of each country, which undoubtedly has differences, however minor they may be, there is external law, namely international law, namely the European Convention on Human Rights, which provides for freedom of expression as one of the human rights, and which is implemented in all Western Balkan countries, including the Republic of Kosovo⁴.

In the context of an analytical overview of the impact of the ECHR decisions on the Western Balkan countries, regarding freedom of expression, we will analyze the countries separately below, dividing them in advance into two groups. The first group includes the Western Balkan countries that are part of the Council of Europe, i.e. can be defendants in the European Court of Human Rights, and the second group includes the state of Kosovo, which is not part of the Council of Europe, i.e. cannot be a defendant in the European Court of Human Rights.

In the work "Freedom of Speech under Attack", the authors analyze how the ECHR has deviated from its early practices regarding political speech, especially through an increasingly restrictive interpretation of expressions that can be considered dangerous to public order or that incite ethnic and religious hatred (Zwart, 2015). This has had a direct impact on Balkan states, which have sometimes used this logic to justify the suppression of critical voices or independent media. Among the most controversial cases dealt with by the ECHR that have had an impact on this region are *Vejdeland and Others v. Sweden* and *Perinçek v. Switzerland*, which addressed the boundaries between freedom of expression and hate speech, setting a precedent for analyses related to genocide denial or divisive political propaganda.

Moreover, according to Harry M. Bracken, the idea that words are separate from deeds is essential in the context of protecting expression: words in themselves do not constitute deeds, unless they are linked to direct incitement to violence or collective hatred (Bracken, 1994). This approach is important for Balkan countries facing political polarization, where the boundaries of political discourse are often selectively interpreted by the authorities.

In this context, the main challenge in the Western Balkans remains finding a balance between the protection of freedom of expression and its legitimate restrictions in accordance with the three-pronged test of Article 10 of the ECHR: compliance with the law, pursuit of a legitimate aim, and necessity in a democratic society.

4. DECISIONS OF THE STRASBOURG COURT REGARDING FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION IN THE WESTERN BALKAN COUNTRIES

a. Republic of Albania - The Republic of Albania, despite the fact that it is a member of the Council of Europe and that its citizens have the right to submit cases to the European Court of Human Rights, has not yet filed a single case regarding the right to freedom of expression as provided for in Article 10 of the ECHR. From the results of the HUDOC⁵, it is noted that the Albanian state has not yet been sued by any person regarding this right. This search result does not mean that the Albanian state has fully respected

² Article 10 of the ECHR:

1. Everyone has the right to freedom of expression. This right shall include freedom to hold opinions and to receive and impart information and ideas without interference by public authority and regardless of frontiers. This Article shall not prevent States from requiring the licensing of broadcasting, television or cinema enterprises.

2. The exercise of these freedoms, since it carries with it duties and responsibilities, may be subject to such formalities, conditions, restrictions or penalties as are prescribed by law and are necessary in a democratic society, in the interests of national security, territorial integrity or public safety, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, for the protection of the reputation or rights of others, for preventing the disclosure of information received in confidence, or for maintaining the authority and impartiality of the judiciary.

³ Croatia is also considered a Western Balkan country, but with its entry into the European Union, it is now generally not included in the group of Western Balkan countries.

⁴ The Republic of Kosovo implements it in a special way since it is not part of the Council of Europe, while other states are obliged to implement the Convention and the decisions of the ECHR, since they are members of the Council of Europe.

⁵ <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/> (22.03.2025)

this right, but at least it indicates two things, and that either the Albanian state has managed to protect this right through domestic legal mechanisms, or that those who have suffered from the violation of freedom of expression have not been able or have not wanted to send the case to the ECHR, and the latter seems to be closer to the truth.

b. Republic of North Macedonia- The Republic of North Macedonia has been a defendant in the European Court of Human Rights 19 times, alleging that it has violated freedom of expression, a right guaranteed by Article 10 of the ECHR. The result of the Macedonian state is not good at all, since in all the claims it has been found that North Macedonia has violated freedom of expression, which makes this state ranked in an unenviable position in respect of the ECHR, namely its Article 10. In one case, the Republic of North Macedonia had convicted a senior member of a political party for the criminal offense of defamation, after this person had made two statements that were considered defamatory, one of them related to the alleged misuse of DSK wiretapping equipment in connection with trading on the stock exchange, while the other related to the sale of state-owned construction land in the central area of the city of Skopje. The declarant at the time of making these statements was the vice-chairman of the opposition political party and a member of the Assembly. The ECHR in both cases found that the applicant's criminal conviction constituted an interference, namely an interference with the applicant's freedom of expression, that such an interference was in accordance with the law, namely it was based on the then valid provisions of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Macedonia; that both procedures had an identical legitimate aim – protection of the authority of S. M., but also that in both cases the applicant's criminal conviction as an intervention, namely an interference with the applicant's freedom of expression, was not proportionate in relation to the legitimate aim for the realization of which efforts were made to achieve, namely that the criminal conviction “was not necessary in a democratic society”, in accordance with Article 10 paragraph 2 of the ECHR (Rights, 2018).

In another case, North Macedonia was found to have violated freedom of expression when it removed from the Parliament lobby several journalists who were reporting on events taking place in the parliamentary session, their removal being forcible with the use of Parliament security. According to the ECHR, this was deemed to have violated the freedom of expression (Rights, 2017).

c. Republic of Serbia - The Republic of Serbia is among the Western Balkan countries that has been sued the most in the European Court of Human Rights. There are a total of 8 cases filed where the subjects have claimed that Serbia has violated freedom of expression. From the results of the research regarding the Serbian state, it is noted that this state has violated freedom of expression in most cases, for which the European Court of Human Rights itself has stated that there has been a violation of Article 10 of the European Convention on Human Rights (Database, a.d.).

d. Republic of Montenegro - The Republic of Montenegro enjoys a very good record in terms of the number of cases filed against it at the European Court of Human Rights, since so far only two cases have been filed and in both cases there has been a violation of freedom of expression by Montenegro (Montenegro, 2015). Thus, we can say that Montenegro also stands at good levels in terms of the cases that are opened against it in the ECHR, but it cannot be said that it stands well in terms of the evaluations it receives in the cases that are opened in this court, since from the two cases presented, both have been lost, being found to have violated the freedom of expression twice.

e. Bosnia and Herzegovina – has a good record in the European Court of Human Rights, at least as regards the right under Article 10 of the ECHR, namely freedom of expression. Only one case has been brought against this country in the ECHR, and in this case, Bosnia and Herzegovina has not violated freedom of expression, so the decisions of the domestic courts have been considered in accordance with the European Convention on Human Rights.

The case presented concerned a Muslim religious community and three NGOs which had sent a letter to the highest authorities of the Brcko district, expressing their concerns regarding the procedure for appointing the director of the multi-ethnic public radio station, alleging that an editor at the station, who had been proposed for that position, had committed acts that were disrespectful to Muslims and ethnic Bosnians. The letter was published in three different daily newspapers, and the editor subsequently filed a defamation lawsuit in a civil court, whereupon the senders of the letter were found liable for defamation and ordered to withdraw the letter ({GC}, 2017). The ECHR concluded that there had been no violation of Article 10 of the Convention, since it was satisfied that the interference complained of was based on relevant and sufficient reasons and that the authorities of the respondent State had struck a balance between the applicants' interest in the right to expression, on the one hand, and the editor's interest in the protection of her reputation, on the other, thus acting within their margin of appreciation ({GC}, 2017).

5. THE REPUBLIC OF KOSOVO AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE ECHR'S DECISIONS REGARDING FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION

The Republic of Kosovo, still not a member of the Council of Europe, cannot be a subject of litigation in the European Court of Human Rights, a right that is in fact directly denied to the citizens of Kosovo who do not have any effective international legal remedy at their disposal to protect freedom of expression, a right guaranteed by the country's own constitution as well as by the European Convention on Human Rights and the Declaration of Fundamental Rights and Freedoms.

Despite the fact that the Republic of Kosovo is not a member state of the Council of Europe, and consequently cannot be forced by this international institution to implement the decisions of the ECHR, it has itself forced itself to interpret the fundamental freedoms and human rights guaranteed by the Constitution of Kosovo and the ECHR, based on the practice of the ECHR. The

Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo expressly provides that: “*Human rights and fundamental freedoms guaranteed by this Constitution shall be interpreted consistent with the court decisions of the European Court of Human Rights*” (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, 2008). Then it is pointed out that: “*Everyone enjoys the right of judicial protection if any right guaranteed by this Constitution or by law has been violated or denied and has the right to an effective legal remedy if found that such right has been violated*” (Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo A., 2008). The Constitution determines that human rights and freedoms, which are provided for one by one with the mentioned international agreements and instruments (Art.22, 2008), guaranteed by it, will be directly applied in the territory of the Republic of Kosovo and will prevail in case of conflict over all legal provisions and other acts of public institutions (Cukalovic, 2013). This means that priority is given here to ratified international agreements, that is, international agreements and instruments, but at the same time it is guaranteed that the provisions on fundamental rights and freedoms are interpreted in favor of the advancement of the values of a democratic society (Cukalovic, 2013). Below we will see some of the ECHR decisions that have had an impact on freedom of expression by further defining and clarifying this right guaranteed by the convention, and that have been applied by the Kosovo judiciary:

- Freedom of expression constitutes one of the main foundations of a democratic society, and one of the basic conditions for its progress and for the personal fulfillment of every individual;
- Freedom of expression constitutes the main foundation of a democratic society and one of the basic conditions for individual progress and fulfillment (Austria, 2003);
- The scope of freedom of expression includes not only the substance of information or ideas, but also the various ways in which they are manifested, transmitted and received (Poland, 2004);
- Freedom of expression applies not only to ‘information’ or ‘ideas’ that are positively received or considered harmless, but also to those that offend, shock or disturb the state or any group of the population. Such are the requirements of pluralism, tolerance and open-mindedness, without which there is no ‘democratic society’ (Case of Handyside v. The United Kingdom, 1976);
- Freedom of expression is not absolute by nature and as such can be limited. This freedom is subject to certain restrictions, provided that these restrictions are "defined by law" and "necessary in a democratic society" (59A, 1991);
- The "necessary in a democratic society" test, whenever there is a violation of Article 10 of the Convention, respectively if the fact that there has been an interference with the right to freedom of expression is proven, requires the Court to decide whether this interference is provided for by law (73, 2001).
- The ECHR has given "special importance" to free political debate and political expression (63, 2009), stating that there is little scope under Article 10, paragraph 2 of the ECHR to limit the freedom of political expression (193, 2015), clarifying that if broad restrictions are allowed for political speech in individual cases, this would undoubtedly affect the respect for freedom of expression in general in the state in question (73, 2001);
- Regarding the freedom of expression on the Internet, the ECtHR has stated that due to the special nature of the Internet, the "tasks and responsibilities" given to news portals for the purposes of Article 10 of the ECHR, may be different to a certain extent from those of traditional publishers in terms of third-party content (133, 2015).
- Freedom of expression includes the publication of political statements, programs of political subjects and photographs as well as the expression of political opinions including the posting of political content on the Internet (251, 2018), etc.

All the decisions of Strasbourg Court have influenced the decisions of the Kosovar judiciary, even now they are included in the practice of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Kosovo as well as in various decisions of the regular Kosovar courts, which during the interpretation of freedom of expression refer to the aforementioned decisions, as well as other decisions of the ECtHR, since these decisions are a special type of source of law for the Republic of Kosovo.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis made in this paper shows that the ECHR plays an irreplaceable role in guaranteeing and protecting freedom of expression in the Western Balkans countries. Countries such as North Macedonia and Serbia have been faced with a significant number of cases in which violations of Article 10 of the Convention have been found, highlighting the need for further reforms within the justice system and the guarantee of fundamental rights. In contrast, Albania and Bosnia and Herzegovina have a low number of cases filed, although this does not exclude the need for greater institutional vigilance in preventing potential violations. Montenegro, although with few cases, has been convicted in all of them, which indicates challenges in the practical implementation of international standards. The Republic of Kosovo constitutes a unique case. Although it is not a party to the Convention and does not have access to the ECHR, it has taken an important step by making the practice of the ECHR part of its own legal system. The Constitution of Kosovo clearly establishes the primacy of international instruments and the obligatory reference to the Strasbourg jurisprudence, demonstrating a clear will to integrate and meet European standards.

In conclusion, it can be said that the role of the ECHR is essential for improving the human rights situation in the region, while the Western Balkan states should be more engaged in the domestic implementation of the decisions of this court. This is the path towards a functional democracy, which respects and protects freedom of expression as one of the most important rights of the individual.

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